

EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF YOUTH LEISURE IN THE MODERN WORLD

Muyassar Asadullayevna Gofurova

Teacher, Namangan Construction-Engineering Institute
Academic lyceum

Annotation: This article is about youth and their today’s problems. It also defines how to organize their free time effectively in the modern world and makes suggestions to improve their role in social life, in addition, gives examples from real life.

Key words: youth leisure, education, “Five Initiatives”, vocational guidance, distance education.

Of course every country’s prosperity and future is estimated with its youth’s strength and capacity. The more educated and patriot they are, the more prosperous and bright our future will be. So, parents try to give good education to their children within they are born and they also want them to be masters of their professions in the future. Abu Rayhan Beruni said: “If you show me youth, I will tell you what tomorrow’s country will look like.” The world famous writer Chingiz Aitmatov said: “If they asked me about the most delicious things in our lives, I would say that I was young and the human spirit is young.” With these words they are a thousand times right because these words are also proof of our opinion. The issue of youth has always been in the public interest. Governments pay more attention to them and spend more money on creating opportunities so they can study and work on themselves in good conditions. For instance, our country Uzbekistan is also essaying to implement our youth with the latest technologies and opportunities in order to study and contribute to the enhancement of our motherland.

There has been much works on improving the role of youth and their active participation in social, political and democratic processes. As the answer to those opportunities, our youth are asked to take responsibilities in the field of education, sports and culture; bring up in a spirit of respecting for national human values; protect the country from different ideological threats and achieve many triumphs in the world’s winning stages as congenial to our government’s attention. Indeed, Uzbekistan needs knowledgeable and educated youth who have the ability of physically and mentally healthy, spiritually mature and intellectually developed, in addition, capable of taking responsibility for the future of the country. The question is that, how to bring up that person?

As we know, while our many youth are achieving good results in different spheres, some others are becoming less active in social life and wasting their time useless things. This is becoming a reason to many troubles and even crimes in society. In order to prevent them, we will have to solve the problem of organizing our youth leisure meaningful. It is so important that many measures are being undertaken and laws are adopted by our government. As proof of that, we can take examples of works carrying out under the leadership of our president Shavkat Mirziyoev. “Action Strategy”, “State Youth Policy” and “Five Initiatives” are clear examples of his policy.

As it is known, the head of state has put forward five important initiatives on social, spiritual and educational activities. The first initiative aims to increase the interest of young people in music, painting, literature, theater and other arts, and to develop their talents. The second initiative is aimed at creating the necessary conditions for the physical education of young people and their sports. A third initiative is to promote the effective use of computer technology and the Internet among the population and youth. The Fourth Initiative aims at creating a systematic work to enhance the spirituality of young people, and to promote wider reading among them. The fifth initiative deals with the employment of women.[2] A lot of measures are being undertaken according to “Fifth Initiatives” today. All of these are aimed at improving the morale of youth and their meaningful leisure.

In short, these five initiatives were met with great interest by the public, especially the youth. Because today we see many local cultural centers, schools of music and art, luxurious libraries and sports centers are being built, many competitions, festivals and conferences are being held among youth and massive works are being carried out for the involvement of them in education and training as the fulfillment of “Fifth Initiatives”. According to the main conclusions of the professional referral query which was conducted on vocational guidance through U-Report by The Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 82% of respondents believe that the state should provide vocational guidance for youth (85% of women responded positively to this, and 80% of men agreed). 57% of respondents believe that they should start vocational guidance at school. 22% of respondents think it should start at kindergarten, and 14% believe that the selection phase should begin within college.[3] From childhood parents must help their children to choose profession according to their abilities and they must be busy with their favorite activities since person who is involved in sports, music, art and education serves and brings profit to nation. Moreover, then, they won't have any time to think of alien ideas. Youth should form the habit of reading books instead of playing computer games and surfing the net all day long after classes. At Institutes and Universities all the students should be occupied with scientific activity. At high

education there is a subject of “Independent study skills” for the first year students. In this subject they learn how to adapt to Institute life, how to organize time, how to do research work and how to study effectively and its strategies. I think this subject should be arranged not only in high education but also at all the educational establishments.

As we know, recently our government gave a vacation ahead of time due to corona virus. As a result, pupils and students had to go back home. And now they have much free time and the problem is how to spend it? It is said that the lessons for school pupils will be hold on TV and for students they will be online by telegram and Moodle system. This global problem increased the demand for distance education and probably, it may help to develop distance education system. In today’s modern world organizing lessons online is good but the question here is what about students who are from remote villages or places where there is no Internet. Don’t they have right to study? Right, there have been many attempts and works related with network system by government. However, this is still one of our weakest points. On the other hand, during vocation pupils and students are involved to do household tasks by their parents. Their action is just like the proverb “When the cat is away, the mice will play”. But parents should give them all the necessary conditions for their reading. They mustn’t consider that the holiday is for having a rest but chance to read more and work on them.

All in all, time passes so quickly that we can’t imagine, therefore, we must organize our leisure time meaningful and usefully. In general, when both the government and parents act together the results will be effective and there will be fewer crimes in society, in addition, country goes in the way of development. Our youth should also recognize our great history and whose generation we are. As our first president Islam Abduganievich Karimov said “There is no future without past” we should know more about them and follow their path in order to take our motherland towards prosperity.

References:

1. Tamara Xo'janova "Problems of perfect protection of the young generation in globalization processes" article, 9th International Conference "Science and practice: a new level of integration in the modern world", November 10,2019, Sheffield, UK.
2. <http://interkomitet.uz/prezident-yoshlar-ma-naviyatini-yuksaltirish-ularning-bo-sh-vaqtini-mazmunli-tashkil-etish-bo-yicha-muhim-vazifalarni-belgilab-berdi/>
3. <https://uzbekistan.ureport.in/story/364/>

